

PROBLEMS OF SOCIOLINGUISTIC RESEARCH ON THE ONTOGENESIS OF
SPEECH.

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the problems of sociolinguistic research on the ontogenesis of speech.

Keywords: world, children's speech, science, definition, various terms, proposition, spiritual values, youth, requirements of the time, basis, teaching, modern method, sources, basis, in-depth study, etc.

The main manifestations of the child's direct experience are the necessary beginning of cognitive processes, a kind of "data collection" about the world around him. Later, children receive knowledge about the world indirectly, with the help of language, through oral communication, books and other sources. It is the transition to more complex images associated with the process of language acquisition that is the result of a certain systematization of already accumulated information using cognitive operations such as categorization, logical conclusions and various transformations.

The phenomenon of the formation of a person's linguistic abilities in ontogenesis cannot be considered without taking into account the communicative, speech-based nature of communication. Entering into constant and infinitely diverse contacts with the environment and society, a person enriches and improves not only social, practical, but also speech and communicative experience, which allows him to achieve success in everyday, personal and professional-business relations. Of course, the formation of these aspects of communicative competence begins with the birth of a person and continues throughout his adult life.

The linguistic competence achieved in the process of speech ontogenesis "results" in a multifaceted and purely individual program of preferences and stereotypes of speech behavior, which form the basis of the "speech portrait" or "idiostyle" of the individual. One of the main aspects of such successful and productive communication is the ability to build one's speech in a collaborative, "friendly" manner, observing the norms and rules of genre design for typical situations of social interaction between people. This study is an attempt to identify and clarify the main patterns of the formation of strategic preferences in genres of negative phatic orientation in ontogenesis using examples of the speech of preschool (4-5 years) and primary school (10-11 years) children. The study is based on K. F. Sedov's concept of types of linguistic personalities according to their ability to cooperate in speech behavior. According to the scientist, the character of a person in communication is clearly manifested in how he builds his relationship with a communication partner, "what path he chooses to achieve a specific communicative goal".

K. F. Sedov identifies conflicting, centralized and cooperative levels of a person's communicative competence. The basis for creating this typology is "attitude to the communication partner. Thus, the conflicting type of communication is characterized by an attitude towards the interlocutor, the centralized type by ignoring him, and the cooperative type by focusing on another participant in the communication".

The basis for determining these levels of communicative competence are strategic stereotypes of a person's speech behavior in the continuum of everyday communication, expressed in the invective, politeness or rational-heuristic direction of phatic speech, which are most clearly manifested in conflict situations. It is known that adults use different communication styles and different strategies

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of speech behavior in everyday practice. However, as a rule, there are stable tendencies towards the use of certain strategic preferences in a conflict situation. In order to determine the presence / absence of such tendencies in the speech practice of children at different stages of ontogenetic development, we conducted a systematic (over a year) observation of everyday communication in children of the middle group. kindergarten (25 people) and 4th grade of a comprehensive school (25 people)¹.

In addition, children were asked to depict a number of plot pictures reflecting a conflict situation, to continue the dialogue with the conflict content according to the proposed beginning, and to dramatize controversial situations within the framework of role-playing games. We note that after completing such diagnostic tasks with children, the possibility of developing dialogue in cooperation and methods of preventing the conflict itself were considered. The main genres of oral conversational speech studied by children of these age groups were the genres of everyday conversation and quarrel. Of particular interest for the analysis were recordings of conflict dialogues in spontaneous oral speech between representatives of both age groups studied (preschooler - junior schoolchild). The conducted studies have shown that the quarrel genre is often used by both preschool and primary school children in everyday communication and is a reflection of the insufficient development of their ability to establish effective verbal communication with people around them.

In preschool childhood, conflict can be a general manifestation of age-related egocentrism, often exacerbated by excessive protection by adults, the absence or lack of ideas about the norms and rules of verbal formation of social interaction with other people. At the age of 4-5, not only the everyday conversational genre, but also the interrogation genre very easily turns into a quarrel genre. This stage of ontogenetic development is characterized by the use of a direct instrumental form of aggression and an invective strategy of verbal behavior.

In general, despite its age-related nature, in the speech behavior of preschool children there is a noticeable tendency towards a conflict or cooperative type with people around them. According to the nature of the teenager's behavior in a conflict, we can talk about his more stable tendency to conflict, a centralized or cooperative type of language personality. The qualitatively high development of the communicative competence of a junior schoolchild allows him not only to significantly "enrich" the speech content of the conflict, but also to use various strategies of speech behavior in its process. The invective speech strategy of behavior in conflict still remains one of the leading methods of adolescent activity.²

One of the problems of sociolinguistic research on the ontogenesis of speech is the process of mastering the rules of "situational and role grammar", which form the basis of the child's socialization.

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